

THEORETICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS FOR MANAGING TEXTILE CLUSTERS AND INCREASING THEIR EXPORT POTENTIAL

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Abstract: *The article deals with theoretical and methodological foundations of textile clusters management and ways to increase their export potential in Uzbekistan. Modern approaches to cluster development are analysed, the key factors influencing the efficiency of textile cluster management are determined, and the necessity of introducing innovative methods and management tools is substantiated.*

Keywords: *textile clusters, management, export potential, competitiveness, cluster development, innovation*

Introduction: The textile industry occupies one of the key places in the structure of Uzbekistan's economy, making a significant contribution to job creation, growth of export earnings and development of related industries. In recent years, the country has been actively pursuing a policy of forming textile clusters aimed at building vertically integrated value chains and increasing the level of added value of manufactured products.

Nevertheless, despite the achieved positive results, a number of important issues remain unresolved in the process of textile clusters development, related to insufficient efficiency of their management, limited innovation activity of enterprises and undisclosed export potential. This actualises the need for theoretical understanding and methodological substantiation of the mechanisms of effective functioning of textile clusters in modern conditions.

The aim of this study is to develop a theoretical and methodological framework for the management of textile clusters in Uzbekistan with a focus on stimulating their export activity.

The relevance of the topic is due to the need to strengthen the competitive position of domestic textile products in international markets, rationalise the use of domestic resources and actively involve national producers in global value chains.

Analysis of literature on the topic: The issues of development and management of industrial clusters have been widely reflected in the scientific works of both foreign and domestic researchers. The theoretical aspects of the formation of cluster structures were considered in detail by M. Porter [1], who described clusters as territorially concentrated associations of interrelated companies and organisations that contribute to the growth of competitiveness and stimulate innovation processes (Porter, 1998). In his model, a special place is given to the influence of clusters on the economic development of countries and strengthening of their export positions.

In the specifics of the textile industry, the issues of clustering were highlighted in the works of M.L. Bazarov and Sh.H. Babaev[2], who analyse the processes of creating textile clusters in Uzbekistan. The authors emphasise the importance of clusters for the development of agro-industrial complex, deepening the processing of

raw materials and increasing the export potential of the industry. At the same time, they emphasise the need to improve management mechanisms, introduce innovations and improve the qualifications of personnel to ensure the sustainability of cluster development.

In foreign studies, in particular, in the works of R. Gereffi and G. Humphrey, the emphasis is made on the role of vertical integration in the textile industry as the most important factor in the formation of competitive advantages. The authors emphasise the need for active participation of enterprises in global value chains to increase their export activity.

Despite the accumulated scientific experience, the issues of complex theoretical and methodological support of effective management of textile clusters in order to increase their export potential in the specific conditions of Uzbekistan remain underdeveloped. The existing approaches require further adaptation to the peculiarities of national economic development, institutional environment and global market requirements.

Thus, a comprehensive analysis and development of practice-oriented recommendations for the effective management of textile clusters is of particular relevance and necessitates the present study. [3]

The review of scientific works allows us to conclude that, despite the active development of the theory of clustering and the existence of extensive research on the management of industrial clusters, there is a lack of works devoted to the comprehensive substantiation of theoretical and methodological foundations for the management of textile clusters, taking into account the peculiarities of socio-economic development of Uzbekistan and the need to increase their export potential.

Most of the existing management models require adaptation to national specifics and modern requirements of the global economy, which emphasises the relevance of further research in this direction.

In this regard, the development of new methodological approaches focused on the effective functioning of textile clusters and their integration into international value chains is of particular importance.

This study aims to fill the identified scientific gaps by developing theoretical and methodological foundations for the management of textile clusters in Uzbekistan with a focus on strengthening their export activity.

Materials and methods: Both theoretical and empirical methods were used in the research process.

As a theoretical basis of the work we analysed modern scientific publications of domestic and foreign authors devoted to the problems of clustering, management of industrial clusters, development of the textile industry and formation of export potential. Particular attention is paid to the works that consider the specifics of cluster functioning in countries with transition economies and in the context of integration into global markets.

The empirical basis of the study was formed by statistical data of state bodies of the Republic of Uzbekistan, reports of textile clusters, international organisations (World Bank, UNIDO), as well as analytical materials of industry associations.

The following research methods were used to achieve the set objectives:

- comparative and system analysis of theoretical approaches to the development of cluster structures;
- structural and functional analysis of textile clusters in Uzbekistan;
- method of generalisation and analogies to identify effective management practices;
- methods of statistical data processing to assess the dynamics of industry development and export indicators;
- expert assessments to identify the factors constraining the growth of textile clusters in Uzbekistan. [4]

The integrated use of these methods allowed to provide a holistic understanding of the problem under study and to develop sound recommendations for improving the management of textile clusters.

Analyses and Results: The following results were obtained in the course of the study:

-analysis of existing theoretical approaches to cluster development in the textile sector has shown that the main cluster models proposed by both foreign and domestic scholars require adaptation to the specifics of Uzbekistan. The key problems are insufficient degree of vertical integration, weak interaction between different supply chain actors and underdeveloped infrastructure to support sustainable cluster development.

-a study of Uzbekistan's textile clusters revealed several structural features. Most clusters are concentrated in regions where raw material (cotton) production predominates, but to develop processing and increase export potential it is necessary to strengthen the role of small and medium-sized enterprises, as well as to create modern production and logistics complexes.

-methodological substantiation of textile cluster management has shown that in order to increase export potential it is necessary to introduce modern management technologies, including the system of integrated management, increasing the level of information technology and developing human resources. An important factor is the improvement of coordination between state bodies and private enterprises.

-practical recommendations suggested by the study include improving infrastructure and logistics, strengthening support for innovative projects in the textile sector, and developing educational and scientific initiatives to improve the skills of workers. In addition, greater participation in global value chains is needed, which would significantly improve Uzbekistan's export position.

Discussing these results, it should be noted that despite the presence of positive dynamics in the development of textile clusters, significant barriers to increasing their export potential remain. Especially important is the fact that cluster development requires not only the creation of a favourable institutional environment, but also close cooperation with international partners to attract investment and new technologies.

The problems identified in the course of the study require a comprehensive approach to solving, and the proposed recommendations can serve as a basis for the formation of effective policies for textile clusters. [5]

Conclusions and suggestions: Based on the conducted research, the following conclusions can be drawn:

-textile clusters in Uzbekistan have a high potential for growth, but their development is limited by a number of factors such as insufficient vertical integration, weak infrastructure and limited innovation capacity. These problems hinder the full realisation of the industry's export potential.

-methodological approaches to textile cluster management require further elaboration taking into account the specifics of the transition economy of Uzbekistan. In particular, it is necessary to develop adapted management models that will take into account the peculiarities of the national institutional environment, economic realities and international requirements.

-the need for state support and the creation of an effective institutional environment for the successful functioning of textile clusters is one of the key issues requiring attention from the authorities. In particular, it is necessary to create mechanisms to simplify bureaucratic procedures, develop infrastructure and stimulate innovative activity.

-Uzbekistan needs to actively integrate into international value chains, which will require increasing technological awareness and product quality, as well as active participation in global trade and production agreements.

-clustering of the textile industry requires better coordination between public and private entities, which would allow for more flexible and competitive export-oriented production and distribution chains.

Based on the findings, the following recommendations can be proposed:

-development of infrastructure: creation of specialised zones for textile clusters with modern logistical and technological infrastructure, which will contribute to cost reduction and improvement of product quality.

-increasing the level of innovation activity: stimulation of scientific and technological research in the textile industry, introduction of innovative methods of production and use of new materials.

-state support: development and implementation of a state programme to support textile exports, including tax incentives and subsidies for textile enterprises participating in cluster projects.

-human resources policy: creation of a system of professional education and advanced training for specialists working in the textile industry, as well as development of programmes for training managers with the necessary competencies for cluster management.

-strengthening international relations: active participation in international exhibitions, trade missions and conclusion of agreements with foreign partners to expand the market for textile products.

The proposed recommendations can become the basis for the formation of an effective policy in the development of textile clusters in Uzbekistan, which will ensure the growth of export potential and strengthen the competitiveness of the industry in the world market.

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